

Kilmarie, Ls 20° (Fall)

2384 (sol n)



2389 (sol n+5)



2405 (sol n+21)



Mary Anning 3, Ls 275° (Summer)

2870 (sol n)



2874 (sol n+4)



2882 (sol n+12)

